

Consent Form for Participation in the Research Project

Dear Sir/Madam,

The information regarding this research is provided in this document. By this letter, you are invited to participate in this study. Participation is entirely voluntary, and you are free to choose whether or not to take part in this research.

You are not required to make an immediate decision, and you may take your time to consider your participation. You can ask any questions you may have from the research team and consult with anyone you wish. Before signing this consent form, ensure that you understand all the information presented in this document and that all your questions have been answered.

Principal Investigator

1. I understand that the purpose of this research is to evaluate the effectiveness of rehabilitation through attention training exercises (visual, auditory, and combined) in adults with chronic tinnitus.
2. I acknowledge that my participation in this research is entirely voluntary and that I am not obligated to take part in this study. I have been assured that if I choose not to participate, I will not be deprived of standard diagnostic and therapeutic care, and my treatment relationship with the medical center and my physician will not be affected.
3. I understand that even after agreeing to participate, I may withdraw from the study at any time by informing the investigator. My withdrawal will not result in the denial of routine medical services.
4. My participation in this research will include the following:
 - Completing an initial information form, as well as tinnitus, depression, and anxiety questionnaires.
 - Undergoing hearing and tinnitus evaluations by an audiologist.
 - Performing attention tests and EEG recordings.
 - If required, I will receive an exercise program and return for follow-up evaluations after a specified period.
5. The potential benefits of participating in this study include:
 - By participating in this research, upon completing all stages, I will receive a payment for my participation.

6. The risks and possible side effects of participation in this study are as follows:
 - This study does not pose any foreseeable risks to my health.
7. I understand that all information related to me will be kept strictly confidential by the research team. They are only permitted to publish general and group-based results without mentioning my name or personal details.
8. I acknowledge that the Research Ethics Committee has access to my information for the purpose of ensuring my rights are protected.
9. I understand that I will not be responsible for any costs related to research interventions.
10. I have been introduced to **Mr. Hossein Namvar Arefi** as the principal investigator and have been informed that I can contact him if I have any concerns or questions about my participation.
 - **Contact number:** +989120759684
11. I understand that if I experience any physical or psychological issues due to participation in this study, the investigator will be responsible for providing appropriate treatment and covering related costs.
12. If I have any complaints or objections regarding the research process or personnel, I can contact the **Research Ethics Committee of Iran University of Medical Sciences** at the following address:
 - **Address:** Hemmat Highway - Near Milad Tower - Iran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran. **Postal Code:** 1449614535

This informed consent form has been prepared in two copies, with one copy given to me and the other retained by the investigator.

I have read and understood the above information and, based on this, I voluntarily consent to participate in this study.

Participant's Signature

I, **Hossein Namvar Arefi**, am committed to fulfilling all obligations mentioned above and ensuring the safety and rights of participants in this study.

Principal Investigator's Stamp and Signature